

Suitability of Groundwater Quality for Irrigation Use: A Case Study of Basti District (U.P.) India

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Abstract : *The agricultural sector faces increasing pressure to adopt sustainable practices, with water quality being a crucial factor influencing plant growth and soil health. This study assesses groundwater quality for irrigation suitability in the Basti district's aquifer, focusing on several key water quality indices. Agriculture is the district's primary occupation, with over 40 per cent of the workforce engaged in cultivation and 70.78 per cent of the total area under cultivation. Despite the district's significant groundwater resources, technological advancements in groundwater utilization are lacking. In the 2021-22 period, only 65.67 per cent of the gross annual recharge was used for various needs, indicating considerable potential for expanding groundwater use in irrigation.*

Utilizing data from the Central Ground Water Board's web portal (2019-2022), the analysis covers total dissolved solids, Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR), and various ions such as SO_4^- , Ca^{++} , Cl^- , HCO_3^- , and Na^{++} , along with Electrical Conductivity and pH levels. Correlations between Electrical Conductivity and these constituents reveal significant associations. The findings indicate that out of 14 blocks in the district, groundwater quality in nine blocks is suitable for irrigation, supporting sensitive and semi-tolerant crops. Four blocks exhibit moderate quality, while one block has water quality beyond recommended limits, making it suitable for tolerant crop varieties with proper treatment. Thus, with improved technology and precise water quality management, the district's groundwater could significantly enhance agricultural sustainability in the region.

Key Words: *Groundwater Quality, Electrical Conductivity, Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR), Pearson Correlation, US Salinity Diagram, Irrigation Use*

Introduction

In recent years, many hydro-geologist researchers are concerned with different water sector field in urban and rural regions (Abbasnia 2019, Selvakumar 2017), One of them is groundwater pollution, which has increased due to natural and anthropogenic contaminant loading from emerging agricultural practices and is directly related to land use (Lapworth 2017, Sharma, 2017). In India,

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especially in rural areas, agricultural landscape are the backbone of our economy, and have been shaped by their reliance on groundwater resources for irrigation- a practice that has become deeply intertwined with the nation's cultural and economic fabric over time. Groundwater not only serves as a crucial source of water for drinking and industrial purposes, but it also accounts for over 60 per cent of the total irrigated area in the country (Chinnasamy, 2013). This heavy dependence on ground water has, however, come at a cost , as unsustainable extraction and poor management practices have led to gradual depletion of this finite resources (Chakraborty, 2021) It faces mounting pressure to adopt sustainable practices. For example, the diversity in climate, soil composition and topography at both national and regional level, along with variations in the adoption of farming technologies, farm size, structure, and production focus have significant influence.

The importance of ground water for irrigation in India cannot be overstated. It has always been considered the prime requirement and infrastructure for socio-economic development, and its role is becoming more important due to climate change and emerging uncertainty over the last few decades. Several recent studies have shown that groundwater is highly susceptible to pollution from both natural and anthropogenic activities, such as industry, municipal sewage, and agricultural fields laced with agrochemicals (Dangar, 2021), (Chakraborty, 2021)

The quality of groundwater is as important as its quantity, as it not only determines the growth of plants but also soil texture. It has been reported that 97 per cent of the total fresh water on Earth is underground (Rai and Sharma, 1990). The quality of groundwater varies from place to place and from stratum to stratum. It may also vary with seasonal changes of percolation and drought amount. Almost 20 per cent of worldwide groundwater is utilized for irrigation (Adimalla and Venkatayogi 2018; Dimple, 2022).

Approximately 80 per cent of wastewater worldwide is disposed of into the environment without proper treatment (UNESCO, 2018) causing the deterioration of water quality. Good-quality water has the potential to yield maximum results under good soil conditions. Several studies around the world reveal that due to the use of poor-quality water for irrigation, large parts of agricultural land remain uncultivated due to degradation of soil fertility. Groundwater is decreasing at a rate of 800 km³ per year worldwide. A significant source of depletion of groundwater is irrigated agricultural lands (Burek 2016, Dimple 2022). Therefore, knowledge of the quality of groundwater for irrigation purposes is essential.

The Study Area

The study area, the district of Basti, with 14 development blocks spread over an area of 2688 square kilometers, a population of 2,464,464 (Census, 2011), and a population density of 917 persons/km² (Fig 1). The district lies between the newly created district of Sant Kabir Nagar on the east and Gonda on the west, while to the south, the Ghaghra river separates it from the districts of Ayodhya and Ambedkar Nagar. Physiographically, the district is part of the Ghaghra-Gandak Doab of the

Figure 1: The location of Study Area

'Middle Ganga plain,' which is a seemingly featureless plain with an average height of 124 meters and a gentle slope from the west or northwest to the east or southeast. The Ghaghra is the main stream and is the recipient of all water channels. Kuano, Manuwar, and Aami are other rivers that join the master stream Ghaghra. The district has broad alluvial soil with local differences, particularly in Khaddar and Bhangar land. The mainstay of the district is agriculture because 40.98 per cent of total main workers are engaged in cultivation as cultivators and as agricultural laborers (Census 2011), and secondly, 70.78 per cent of the total area is under cultivation. The net sown area is 196,080 hectares, which is 70.78 per cent of the total geographical area of the district. The study area is well endowed with groundwater resources but due to lack of technological advancement, the present stage of groundwater development is low and lagging behind. In 2021-22 only 65.67 percent of the gross annual recharge of groundwater was drawn for watering the crops, domestic, industrial and other uses. Thus the ground water of the area can to play a major role for economic development of the people of the district in the years to come.

Data and Methodology

Alluvial tract of Basti district is underlain by sands of various grades, gravels, silt and clay. The actual thickness of the sediments is not known as CGWB has not carried out exploration in Basti district and the deepest well-constructed by state government is only down to depth of 134.12 m bgl. The southern part of the district is characterized by thicker aquifers, where sand and gravel predominate over clays. The northern part comprises of thinner granular zones and lenses of sand of varying lateral extent, dominated by thick clay. In this study, 14 representative samples of ground water quality data of each block headquarter of the district has been taken from Central Ground Water Board web portal. The data were analyzed for their chemical composition like contained of total dissolved solids, (TDS), Calcium, Chlorine, Magnesium, Sodium, Iron, Bicarbonate (Table 1). The electrical conductivity (EC), pH, Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR) have also been calculated and finally the results plotted in the US salinity Diagram³ to determine suitability for irrigational use.

An attempt has also been made to correlate these with each other and with electrical conductivity to show the proportionate contribution of these constituents towards causing salinization of the ground water. In specifying the quality characteristics of ground water for irrigation, chemical analysis is normally required includes determination of concentration of inorganic constituents present and measurement of the pH value and the specific electrical conductance.

Criteria to determine the suitability of groundwater for irrigation

Irrigation is one of the main consumers of groundwater in India. Irrigation water quality assessment criteria usually include salinity, sodicity, and ion toxicity. However, the same standards

³ The "U.S. Salinity Diagram" is a graphical representation used in agriculture and soil science to illustrate the relationship between the concentration of soluble salts in irrigation water and the potential for soil salinity problems

Table 1: Chemical Analysis of Ground Water samples in Basti District

Name of the Block	Location of observation well		pH	EC in S/cm	Chemical Constituents (ppm)								Salinity Group	
	0° Latitude	0° Longitude			TDS	Ca ⁺⁺	Cl ⁻	Fe ⁺⁺	HCO ₃ ⁻	Mg ⁺⁺	Na ⁺⁺	SO ₄ ⁻		SAR
Bahadurpur	26.689	82.688	8.12	514.00	328.96	41.33	17.60	0.48	246.23	26.33	17.00	6.97	4.13	C ₂ S ₁
Bankati	26.691	82.881	8.07	433.00	277.12	46.67	11.77	0.28	233.83	19.93	9.17	3.33	2.25	C ₂ S ₁
Basti Sadar	26.800	82.753	7.83	506.67	324.27	45.33	18.73	0.34	260.07	27.60	18.50	11.00	4.33	C ₂ S ₁
Gaur	26.821	82.450	7.79	836.33	535.25	61.33	101.80	0.29	282.67	38.33	44.80	25.93	8.97	C ₃ S ₁
Harraiya	26.828	82.465	7.92	685.33	438.61	46.67	63.90	0.34	264.33	35.87	35.07	42.53	7.72	C ₂ S ₁
Kaptanganj	26.762	82.565	7.94	740.00	473.60	46.67	70.83	0.37	282.57	29.33	54.57	26.67	12.52	C ₂ S ₂
Kudraha	26.615	82.799	8.00	867.67	555.31	81.33	62.93	0.28	333.57	29.60	42.83	24.57	8.13	C ₃ S ₁
Ramnagar	27.061	82.656	7.96	517.67	331.31	40.00	14.07	0.46	278.50	27.47	18.50	1.97	4.50	C ₂ S ₁
Rudauli	27.028	82.815	7.81	1292.67	827.31	46.67	100.63	0.81	480.00	34.80	165.90	95.37	36.76	C ₃ S ₄
Saltaua	26.930	82.714	7.88	612.33	391.89	42.67	21.10	0.39	317.07	34.60	23.00	13.93	5.23	C ₂ S ₁
Saughat	26.790	82.645	7.91	511.33	327.25	44.00	17.60	0.40	278.30	28.27	14.00	3.33	3.29	C ₂ S ₁
Vikramjot	26.780	82.366	8.02	576.67	369.07	60.00	18.80	0.52	314.97	22.00	23.13	0.00	5.11	C ₂ S ₁
Dubaulya	26.813	82.476	8.12	821.33	525.65	33.33	75.83	0.26	321.20	53.00	41.57	33.27	8.95	C ₃ S ₁
Parasrampur	26.905	82.3397	7.95	585.00	374.40	53.33	23.77	0.45	300.70	29.60	17.50	2.53	3.84	C ₂ S ₁

Source : Based on Central ground water Board webportal , New Delhi

Ca⁺⁺ - Calcium, Cl⁻ Chlorine, Fe⁺⁺ - Ferric cation, HCO₃⁻ Bicarbonate, Mg⁺⁺ Magnesium, Na⁺⁺ Sodium, SO₄⁻ Sulphate , SAR- Sodium Adsorption Ratio

may not be applicable if the water is utilized for domestic use and industrial supply. Physical, chemical, and bacteriological qualities ascertain groundwater suitability for agriculture use (Yadav, 2021). The suitability of groundwater for irrigation is contingent upon the effect of the mineral constituents of water on both plants and the soil (Richard, 1954). Water used for irrigation purposes always contains some amount of dissolved constituents (salts), which are the product of weathering and erosion of rocks and the solution of minerals. Poor-quality water may affect irrigated crops by causing the accumulation of salt in the root zone, leading to loss of soil permeability due to excess sodium or calcium or by containing pathogens that are directly toxic to plants (Jain, 1996).

Water quality criteria for irrigation water generally take into account characteristics such as crop tolerance to salinity, sodium concentration and phototoxic trace elements. The effect of salinity on the osmotic pressure in the unsaturated soil zone is one of the most important water quality considerations, as this influences the suitability of water for plant consumption, growth, flowering, spreading and fruiting. Several other factors bear on water quality criteria for irrigation. The effect of water on irrigated crops depends, for example, on the texture of the soil as well as the physical properties of the specific contaminants in the water. In some countries, two different sets of water quality criteria are developed for sandy soil and clay-based soil to account for different rates of water percolation and accumulation of substances in the root zone. Considering all these factors, the suitability of groundwater has been determined

Results and Discussions

The complete spatial pattern of hydro chemical data of groundwater of the study area is presented in Table 1. The spatial pattern of key parameters is analyzed as followed:

Hydrogen ion (pH)

The pH of groundwater samples has been found to be in the range 7.79–8.12 with an average value of 7.9, which is under the limit with respect to BIS (BIS (2012) and WHO (WHO 2011) in all samples shown in Table 1. The spatial distribution of pH variation indicates that in north western part, east-northern part and south-eastern part shows slightly alkaline water.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

The concentration of total dissolved solids is an important indication of water suitability. Water that contains too much dissolved solids is not suitable. However, due to several complexities involved, a specific limit of permissible salt concentration for irrigation water cannot be fixed because of wide variations in salinity tolerance among different plants and crops. Nevertheless, field plot studies of crops grown on soils that are artificially adjusted to various levels provide valuable information regarding salt tolerance. Table 2 presents the relative tolerance of crops to soil water–salt concentrations for major crop divisions. The criterion applied was the relative yield of the crop on a saline soil compared to its yield on a non-saline soil under similar crop growing conditions.

Within each group, crops are listed in order of increasing salt tolerance. Electrical conductivity values at the top and bottom of each column represent the range of salinity levels at which a 50 percent decrease in yield may be expected. An important factor related to the relationship between crop growth and water quality is drainage. Poor drainage permits salt concentration in the root zone to toxic proportions. Good drainage is crucial for crop growth and prevents concentration in the root zone. Even with good-quality water, poorly drained surfaces may sometimes go out of production (McKee and Bacon, 1953).

Table 2: Relative tolerances of crops to salt concentration (after Richards 1954)

Crop division	Low salt tolerance	Medium salt tolerance	High salt tolerance
Fruits Crops	Lemon, Peach Strawberry, Plum Almond, Orange Apple, Pear	Date, Olive, Fig Pomegranate	Date palm
Vegetable crops	3000 mhos/cm Green beans Radish 4000 mhos/cm	4000 mhos/cm Cucumber, Squash Peas, Onions, Carrot, Potato, Cabbage 10000 mmhos/cm	1000 mhos/cm Spinach, Kale Garden feet 12000 mmhos/cm
Food Crops	4000 mmhos/cm Gram, Arhar, Moong, Pea 6000 mmhos/cm	6000 mmhos/cm Wheat, Rice, Millet Maize 10000 mmhos/cm	10000 mmhos/cm Barley, Sugarcane Sugerbeet 16000 mmhos/cm

Note: Electrical conductivity values represent salinity levels of the saturation extract at which a 50 percent decrease in yield may be expected as compared to yield on non-saline soil under comparable growing conditions. The saturation extract is the solution extracted from a soil at its saturation percentages.

Source : Todd, D.K (1959) , *Ground water Hydrology*, John Wiley and Sons, New York

Thus, the suitability of water can be correctly judged from TDS only if (i) the percentage of constituents of TDS is known, (ii) the soil type, concentration of salt in it, and drainage conditions are known and (iii) the cropping pattern is known. In the study area, the total dissolved solids range from 277 to 827 ppm (Table 1). The higher value occurs in Gaur, Harraiya, Kaptanganj, Kudraha, Dubauliya and Rudhauili development block (Table 3). The iso-lines for TDS in the area are shown in (fig 2).

Figure 2: Spatial Pattern of Total Dissolved Solids of Ground Water in Aquifers Tapped by Different wells during 2022-23

The higher total dissolved solids in these blocks are due to the natural geology of the region, intensive agricultural practices, and the use of fertilizers and pesticides, which introduce various ions into the groundwater. These blocks have low-gradient topography, and the disposal of untreated domestic wastewater introduces a range of dissolved solids into the groundwater.

Table 3: Suitability of Groundwater for Irrigation Based on TDS and pH Value

Content of TDS ppm	Suitable	Unsuitable	No of sample	Blocks
Up to 400	All water is generally fit for irrigation		8	Bahadurpur, Bankati, Basti sadar, Ramnagar, Saltaua, Sahughat, Vikramjot and Parasrampur
400-600	pH < 9.0	pH > 9.0	5	Gaur, Harraiya, Kaptanganj, Kudraha, and Dubauliya
600-800	pH < 8.5	pH > 8.5	-	
800-1000	pH < 8.0	pH > 8.0	1	Rudhauri
1000-1200	-	Doubtful for irrigation		
>1200	-	Generally unfit for irrigation	-	

Source : Uttar Pradesh Irrigation Research Institute , *Quality of Ground Waters in Ganga – Ghaghra Doab* , Technical Memo, No 42 R-R (G-5) Roorkee, 1971

From Table 3, it is evident that out of the 14 samples, 8 samples (57 per cent) fall within the permissible limit, while the remaining 5 samples (35 per cent) are out of the permissible limit. They are unsuitable for irrigation purposes based on the TDS level. The groundwater samples of Blocks - Bahadurpur, Bankati, Basti Sadar, Ramnagar, Saltaua, Sahughat, Vikramjot and Parasrampur, which exhibit low salt concentration (up to 400 ppm), are suitable and can be very safely used for irrigation without any salinity treatment. Five samples falling within the moderate category can also be utilized for irrigation, provided appropriate salinity control/ treatment techniques are employed. None of the blocks in the district exhibit heavy salt concentrations, thus, there is no need to implement salinity treatment measures for water used in irrigation purposes.

Electrical Conductivity

In water quality determinations, conductivity, reported in micro-mhos/cm, determines the concentration of total dissolved solids (TDS). Electrical conductivity (EC) significantly changes with temperature, and it is necessary to refer them to a standard temperature, normally taken as 25^o Centigrade Celsius. In the study area, EC varies from 433 to 1292 micro-mhos/cm (Table-1 and fig-3).

Figure 3: Spatial Patten of Electrical Conductivity of Ground Water in Aquifers Tapped by Different wells during 2022-23

According to Richard's (1954) classification, the following results have been obtained (Table 4). It is evident from the table that 10 development blocks of the district have moderate EC (250 to 750 micro-mhos/cm (C_2) category) while only 4 blocks fall into the category of C_3 (750 to 2250 micro-mhos/cm). Hence, all the development blocks are safe and suitable for groundwater irrigation. (fig.) 3.

Figure 4. Ground Water Salinity of Basti District (Based on Electrical Conductivity in micro mhos/cm)

Sodium Adsorption Ratio

Kelley (1951) first emphasized the importance of sodium concentration in assessing the suitability of groundwater for irrigation. However, in 1954, the US Salinity Laboratory proposed replacing the sodium percentage concept with a significant ratio termed the Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR), as it directly correlates with the adsorption of sodium by soil. SAR is calculated as follows: $SAR = (Na^{+}/Ca^{+} + Mg^{2+})/2$

Where ionic concentrations are expressed in milliequivalents per liter

Table 4: Electrical Conductivity of Groundwater in Basti District

EC	Types of water	Suitability for irrigation	No of sample	Name of the blocks
Below 250	Low saline (C_1)	Entirely Safe	Nil	
250-750	Moderate Saline (C_2)	Safe under practically all condition	10	Bahadurpur, Bankati, Basti sadar, Harraiya, Kaptanganj, Ramnagar, Saltaua, Sahughat, Vikramjot, and Parasrampur
750-2250	Medium to high saline (C_3)	Safe only with permeable soils and moderate leaching	4	Gaur, Kudraha, Rudhauri and Dubauliya
2250-4000	High Saline (C_4)	Unfair for irrigation	-	-
4000-6000	Very high Saline (C_5)	Unfair for irrigation	-	-
Above 6000	Excessive Saline	Unfair for irrigation	-	-

Source : Richards, L.A (ed) *Diagnosis and Improvement of Saline and Alkaline Soils, Agriculture Handbook 60 , U.S Department of Agriculture , Washington , D.C , 1954*

Richard (1954) classified irrigation water based on sodium adsorption ratios. According to his classification, water is considered excellent if the SAR is between 0 to 10, good if it ranges from 10 to 18, fair if the ratio falls between 18 to 28, and poor if it exceeds 28. The classification of groundwater in the study area regarding SAR indicates a range from low to very high sodium levels for irrigation purposes. Plotting SAR and EC values of the groundwater of the study area reveals that SAR

Table 5: Result of irrigation water on Sodium Adsorption Ratio

SAR	Types of water	Number of sample	Name of the blocks
0-10	Low Sodium Water (S_1)	12	Bahadurpur, Bankati, Basti Sadar, Gaur, Harraiya, Kudraha, Ramnagar, Saltaua, Sahughat, Vikramjot, Daubauliya and pararampur
10-18	Medium Sodium Water (S_2)	1	Kaptanganj
18-28	High Sodium Water (S_3)	-	-
Over 28	Very High Sodium Water (S_4)	1	Rudhauri

Source : Richards, L.A (ed) *Diagnosis and Improvement of Saline and Alkaline Soils, Agriculture Handbook 60 , U.S Department of Agriculture, Washington, D.C, 1954*

values for groundwater samples ranges from 2.25 to 36.76 PPM, indicating low to very high sodium hazards. Out of the 14 samples, groundwater samples from 12 Stations belong to C_2S_1 to C_3S_1 class (low to moderate sodium hazard) while the remaining two samples fall under classes C_2S_2 to C_3S_4 (high to very high sodium). (See Table 5, Fig. 5)

Figure 5 Ground Water Quality of Basti District (Based on US Salinity Diagram)

Relation to Electrical conductivity with different constituents

The correlation of electrical conductivity with different constituents is equally important. Multivariate correlation analysis between the concentrations of various constituents as well as electrical conductivity has been calculated for all 14 samples, and the results are given in Table 6.

It is apparent from Table 6 that the highest correlation is found between Sodium and Sulfate, showing a very high positive correlation coefficient of the order of 0.94. The correlation Coefficient of electrical conductivity with sodium also shows very high correlation (0.93). If the concentration of sodium, sulfate and values of EC increases in irrigation water, it may exacerbate soil salinity and sodicity problems. Sodium can increase soil salinity by contributing to the total dissolved solids (TDS) concentration, while sulphate can contribute to soil sodicity. Together, these ions can

Table 6: Multivariate Correlation between the water contamination as well as EC (by Pearson Correlation Method)

Parameter	pH	Ca ⁺⁺	Cl ⁻	EC in μ S/cm	TDS	Fe ⁺⁺	HCO ₃ ⁻	Mg ⁺⁺	Na ⁺⁺	SO ₄ ⁻
pH	1.00									
Ca ⁺⁺	-0.16	1.00								
Cl ⁻	-0.35	0.22	1.00							
EC in μ S/cm	-0.36	0.23	0.88	1.00						
TDS	-0.36	0.23	0.88	1.00	1.00					
Fe ⁺⁺	-0.27	-0.13	0.08	0.45	0.45	1.00				
HCO ₃ ⁻	-0.34	0.14	0.55	0.87	0.87	0.70	1.00			
Mg ⁺⁺	-0.05	-0.26	0.65	0.52	0.52	-0.18	0.32	1.00		
Na ⁺⁺	-0.41	0.05	0.73	0.93	0.93	0.67	0.89	0.31	1.00	
SO ₄ ⁻	-0.38	-0.02	0.80	0.92	0.92	0.49	0.79	0.48	0.94	1.00
TH	-0.16	0.54	0.73	0.63	0.63	-0.25	0.40	0.67	0.31	0.41
K	0.41	-0.11	0.38	0.22	0.22	-0.44	0.01	0.74	0.00	0.24

Source: Computed from the Table 1 (using Pearson Correlation Method)

compromise soil health and reduce crop productivity. The correlation coefficient for the other water constituents such as sulphate, calcium, chlorine and magnesium, with electrical conductivity decreases progressively, indicating a proportionately reducing contribution of these constituents towards causing pollution in the groundwater.

Conclusion

From the above discussion, it is clear that 86 percent of the groundwater samples in the study area are within the recommended limit of suitability for irrigation. Based on different parameters, it is noted that TDS value of 8 out of 14 samples falls within the permissible limit. However, 6 samples have high TDS content, with their EC values ranging from medium to high salinity group (750-2250 micro mhos/cm) rendering them unsuitable for irrigation. The water of 8 samples have EC below 750 micro-mhos/cm is considered safe for irrigation under practically all conditions. The remaining samples, with EC between 750-2250 micro-mhos /cm can be used for irrigation only with permeable soils and moderate leaching conditions.

According to the US salinity diagram, 9 samples water associated with Medium salinity and low sodium fall in the C₂S₁ group of the salinity diagram. While 3 samples belong to high salinity and low sodium group i.e. C₃S₁. These are moderately suitable for irrigation and can be used to

Figure 6: Location of samples in US Salinity Diagram

irrigate Salt-tolerant and semi tolerant crops under favorable drainage conditions. The water sample of one well associated with medium salinity and medium sodium hazard, falls under C_2S_2 group of the salinity diagram. The remaining 1 sample is associated with high salinity with very sodium hazards and fall in C_3S_4 group of the US salinity diagram (Fig-6).

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